

Matriks Permutasi

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Definisi

- **Matriks:** $A \equiv [\underline{a}_1 \quad \underline{a}_2 \quad \underline{a}_3 \quad \cdots \quad \underline{a}_n]$ dengan $\underline{a}_j \in R^n$
- **Vektor Basis:** $\underline{e}_i = [0 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0]^T$
- **Relasi:** $Ae_i = a_i$, kolom ke- i matriks A

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{e}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 5 \\ 8 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{kolom ke - 2 matriks } A$$

Definisi (lanjutan)

- **Matriks:** $P \equiv I - (\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)(\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)^T$, dengan $i \neq j$

$$P \equiv P_{i,j} = P_{1,2}, \quad i=1 \text{ dan } j=2$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right)^T =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} [1 \quad -1 \quad 0] \right) =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ tukar baris -1 dan baris -2}$$

Matriks P simetris, $P^T=P$

$$\begin{aligned}P^T &= \left(I - (\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)(\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)^T \right)^T \\&= I^T - \left((\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)(\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)^T \right)^T \\&= I - \left((\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)^T \right)^T (\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)^T \\&= I - (\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)(\underline{e}_i - \underline{e}_j)^T \\&= P\end{aligned}$$

Manfaat matriks P

- Untuk pertukaran baris:

$$\begin{aligned} PA &= \left(I - (\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)(\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)^T \right) A \\ &= A - (\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)(\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)^T A \quad ; \text{ distributive ?} \\ &= A - (\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)(\underline{e}_1^T A - \underline{e}_2^T A) \\ &= A - \underline{e}_1 \underline{e}_1^T A + \underline{e}_1 \underline{e}_2^T A + \underline{e}_2 \underline{e}_1^T A - \underline{e}_2 \underline{e}_2^T A \end{aligned}$$

$$PA = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix} = \dots = \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix}$$

Baris-1 dan baris-2 matriks A bertukar tempat.

Manfaat matriks P (lanjutan)

- Untuk pertukaran kolom:

$$\begin{aligned}AP &= A \left(I - (\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)(\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)^T \right) \\ &= A - A(\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)(\underline{e}_1 - \underline{e}_2)^T \\ &= A - (A\underline{e}_1 - A\underline{e}_2)(\underline{e}_1^T - \underline{e}_2^T) \\ &= A - A\underline{e}_1\underline{e}_1^T + A\underline{e}_1\underline{e}_2^T + A\underline{e}_2\underline{e}_1^T - A\underline{e}_2\underline{e}_2^T\end{aligned}$$

$$AP = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \dots = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 5 & 4 & 6 \\ 8 & 7 & 9 \end{bmatrix}$$

Kolom-1 dan kolom-2 matriks A bertukar tempat.

Manfaat matriks P (selesai)

Cermati beda antara:

$$FA = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

dan

$$AP = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 9 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 0 & 0 \\ 7 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 7 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 5 & 0 & 0 \\ 8 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 5 & 0 \\ 0 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Kesimpulan

1. **$PA = P_{ij}A$: baris-i dan baris-j matriks A bertukar tempat.**
2. **$AP = AP_{ij}$: kolom-i dan kolom-j matriks A bertukar tempat.**
3. **Disebut matriks permutasi, apakah:**
 - **Karena PA dan AP merupakan permutasi himpunan $\{PA\}$, atau**
 - **Karena permutasi himpunan elemen $\{\text{baris-i baris-j}\}$ dan atau himpunan elemen $\{\text{kolom-i kolom-j}\}$,
silahkan memilih alasan yang dianggap tepat.**